

$$\boxed{\nabla_{\mu} F^{\mu\nu} = 0}$$

$$\boxed{A_{\mu} dx^{\mu} = A_t dt + A_{\phi} d\phi}$$

(M/1)

$$F_{rt} = \partial_r A_t \quad F_{r\phi} = \partial_r A_{\phi}$$

$$F_{zt} = \partial_z A_t \quad F_{z\phi} = \partial_z A_{\phi}$$

$$\nabla_{\mu} F^{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|g|}} \partial_{\mu} [\sqrt{|g|} F^{\mu\nu}] = 0 \Rightarrow \boxed{\partial_{\mu} [\sqrt{|g|} F^{\mu\nu}] = 0}$$

$$\boxed{\nabla = \phi} \quad \partial_{\mu} [\sqrt{|g|} F^{\mu\phi}] = \partial_r [\sqrt{|g|} F^{r\phi}] + \partial_z [\sqrt{|g|} F^{z\phi}] = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} F^{r\phi} &= F_{\alpha\beta} g^{\alpha r} g^{\beta\phi} = F_{rs} g^{rs} g^{\beta\phi} = F_{rt} g^{rr} g^{t\phi} + F_{r\phi} g^{rr} g^{\phi\phi} = \\ &= (\partial_r A_t) \frac{1}{e^{2\gamma}} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2} + (\partial_r A_{\phi}) \frac{1}{e^{2\gamma}} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2} = \frac{1}{e^{2\gamma} r^2} [\omega (\partial_r A_t) + \partial_r A_{\phi}] \end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{\partial_r [\sqrt{|g|} F^{r\phi}] = \partial_r \left[\frac{r e^{2\gamma}}{f} \cdot \frac{1}{e^{2\gamma} r^2} (\omega (\partial_r A_t) + \partial_r A_{\phi}) \right] = \partial_r \left[\frac{1}{r} (\partial_r A_{\phi} + \omega (\partial_r A_t)) \right]}$$

$$F^{z\phi} = F_{\alpha\beta} g^{\alpha z} g^{\beta\phi} = F_{zs} g^{zs} g^{\beta\phi} = F_{zt} g^{zz} g^{t\phi} + F_{z\phi} g^{zz} g^{\phi\phi} = \frac{1}{e^{2\gamma} r^2} [\omega (\partial_z A_t) + \partial_z A_{\phi}]$$

$$\boxed{\partial_z [\sqrt{|g|} F^{z\phi}] = \partial_z \left[\frac{r e^{2\gamma}}{f} \cdot \frac{1}{e^{2\gamma} r^2} (\omega \partial_z A_t + \partial_z A_{\phi}) \right] = \partial_z \left[\frac{1}{r} (\partial_z A_{\phi} + \omega (\partial_z A_t)) \right]}$$

$$\boxed{v=t}$$

$$\partial_m [\log F^{nt}] = 0$$

(1/2)

$$\underline{\partial_r [\log F^{rt}] + \partial_z [\log F^{zt}] = 0}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{F^{nt}} &= F_{yz} \cdot g^{yr} \cdot g^{zt} = F_{yz} g^{rr} \cdot g^{zt} = F_{rz} \cdot g^{rr} \cdot g^{tt} + F_{r\phi} \cdot g^{rr} \cdot g^{\phi t} = \\ &= (\partial_r A_t) \cdot \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \cdot \left[\frac{f^2 \omega^2 \ominus r^2}{r^2 \cdot f} \right] + (\partial_r A_\phi) \cdot \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \cdot \frac{f\omega}{r} = \underbrace{\frac{(\partial_r A_t) [f^2 \omega^2 \ominus r^2]}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} + (\partial_r A_\phi) \cdot \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}}}_{\text{}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{\log F^{nt}} &= \left(\frac{r e^{2\gamma}}{f} \right) \left[\frac{(\partial_r A_t) (f^2 \omega^2 \ominus r^2)}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \right] + \frac{r e^{2\gamma}}{f} \cdot \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} (\partial_r A_\phi) = \\ &= \frac{1}{r f} [(\partial_r A_t) (f^2 \omega^2 \ominus r^2)] + \frac{f \omega}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi) = \partial_r A_t \cdot \frac{f \omega^2}{r f} \ominus (\partial_r A_t) \frac{r^2}{r \cdot f} + \frac{f \omega}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi) = \\ &= (\partial_r A_t) \cdot \frac{f \omega^2}{r} + \frac{f \omega}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi) \ominus \frac{\partial_r A_t \cdot r}{f} = \boxed{\frac{f \omega}{r} [(\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t)] \ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_r A_t)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{F^{zt}} &= F_{yz} \cdot g^{yz} \cdot g^{zt} = F_{yz} \cdot g^{zz} \cdot g^{zt} = F_{z\phi} \cdot g^{zz} \cdot g^{\phi t} = \\ &= (\partial_z A_t) \cdot \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \cdot \left[\frac{f^2 \omega^2 \ominus r^2}{r^2 \cdot f} \right] + (\partial_z A_\phi) \cdot \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \cdot \frac{f\omega}{r} = \underbrace{\frac{\partial_z A_t [f^2 \omega^2 \ominus r^2]}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} + (\partial_z A_\phi) \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}}}_{\text{}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{\nabla_{\theta}^2 F^{2t}} &= \frac{r e^{2\theta}}{f} \left[\frac{\partial^2 A_t}{r^2 e^{2\theta}} (f^2 \omega^2 \ominus r^2) + (\partial^2 A_{\theta}) \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\theta}} \right] = \frac{1}{r f} (\partial^2 A_t) (f^2 \omega^2 \ominus r^2) + \frac{\omega \cdot f}{r} (\partial^2 A_{\theta}) = \textcircled{1/3} \\ &= \frac{f \omega^2}{r} (\partial^2 A_t) \ominus \frac{r}{f} \partial^2 A_t + \frac{\omega f}{r} (\partial^2 A_{\theta}) = \boxed{\frac{f \omega}{r} [(\partial^2 A_{\theta}) + \omega (\partial^2 A_t)] \ominus \frac{r}{f} \partial^2 A_t} \end{aligned}$$

$$\partial_r [\nabla_{\theta}^2 F^{2t}] + \partial_z [\nabla_{\theta}^2 F^{2t}] = 0$$

$$\partial_r \left[\frac{f \omega}{r} (\partial_r A_{\theta} + \omega \partial_r A_t) \ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\frac{f \omega}{r} (\partial_z A_{\theta} + \omega \partial_z A_t) \ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_z A_t) \right] = 0$$

$$\partial_r [\nabla_{\theta}^2 F^{r\phi}] + \partial_z [\nabla_{\theta}^2 F^{z\phi}] = 0$$

$$\partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_{\phi} + \omega \partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_{\phi} + \omega \partial_z A_t) \right] = 0$$

$$\partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + \omega \partial_z A_t) \right] = 0$$

$$\equiv \vec{A}_{3,r}$$

$$\equiv \vec{\nabla}_z A_3$$

$$\vec{\nabla} = (\partial_r, \partial_z)$$

(M/4)

$$\left| \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \vec{A}_3 = \frac{f}{r} (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \right|$$

$$\epsilon_{i\phi m} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \phi}{\phi} \right) \nabla^m \vec{A}_3$$

$$\nabla_i [\epsilon^{i\phi m} \nabla_m \vec{A}_3] = 0$$

$$\epsilon^{i\phi m} \nabla_i \nabla_m \vec{A}_3 = \underbrace{\epsilon^{r\phi z}}_{\downarrow 1} \nabla_r \nabla_z \vec{A}_3 + \underbrace{\epsilon^{z\phi r}}_{\ominus 1} \nabla_z \nabla_r \vec{A}_3 = 0$$

$\left. \begin{matrix} r\phi \\ z\downarrow \end{matrix} \right\}$

$$\Downarrow \nabla_r \nabla_z \vec{A}_3 = \nabla_z \nabla_r \vec{A}_3$$

$$\boxed{(\vec{a} \times \vec{b} \times \vec{c})_i} = \epsilon_{ikl} a^k (\epsilon^{lab} b_a c_b) = \epsilon_{iku} \epsilon^{lab} a^k b_a c_b = \epsilon_{iku} \epsilon^{lab} a^k b_a c_b =$$

$$= (\delta_{i\ a} \delta_{k\ u} \ominus \delta_{i\ u} \delta_{k\ a}) a^k b_a c_b = \boxed{b_i a^k c_k \ominus a^i b_a c_a}$$

because $\epsilon_{ijl} \nabla^j \nabla^l \neq 0$

$$\left| \underbrace{\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{e}_\phi}_a \times \underbrace{\vec{e}_\phi}_b \times \underbrace{\vec{\nabla} \vec{A}_3}_c = \underbrace{e^\phi \nabla_\phi \vec{A}_3}_b \ominus \underbrace{e^\phi \cdot e_\phi}_1 \cdot \vec{\nabla} \vec{A}_3 = \ominus \vec{\nabla} \vec{A}_3$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_0 \left[\frac{f}{r} \vec{\nabla} \vec{A}_3 \ominus \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t \right] = 0$$

$$\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_\phi = \ominus \left(\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} \vec{A}_3 + \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t \right)$$

$$\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \vec{A}_3 = \frac{f}{r} (\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t)$$

$$\ominus \vec{\nabla} \vec{A}_3 \ominus \frac{f}{r} \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t = \left(\frac{f}{r} \right) \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_\phi \Rightarrow \boxed{\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_\phi = \ominus \frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} \vec{A}_3 \ominus \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t}$$

$$\partial_r \left[\omega \frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \partial_r A_t) \ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\omega \frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + \omega \partial_z A_t) \ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_z A_t) \right] = 0$$

(1/5)

$$\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 = \frac{f}{r} (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t)$$

$$\begin{cases} \vec{\nabla} [\omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 \ominus \frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} A_t] = 0 \\ \vec{\nabla} [\omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t + \frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3] = 0 \end{cases} \Rightarrow \begin{cases} \vec{\nabla} [\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3] = 0 \\ \vec{\nabla} [\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 + \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t] = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\Phi = A_t \ominus i \tilde{A}_3$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_0 \left[\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} \Phi \ominus i \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \Phi \right] = 0$$

Maxwell Eqs.

~~$$\vec{\nabla}_0 \left[\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} (A_t \ominus i \tilde{A}_3) \ominus i \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} (A_t \ominus i \tilde{A}_3) \right] = 0$$~~

~~$$\vec{\nabla}_0 \left[\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus i \frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 \ominus \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t \right] = 0$$~~

$$\vec{\nabla}_0 \left[\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} (A_t \ominus i \tilde{A}_3) \ominus \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} (A_t \ominus i \tilde{A}_3) \right] = 0$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_0 \left[\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus \frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 \ominus i \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 \right] = 0$$

$$\Downarrow \vec{\nabla}_0 \left[\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 \right] = 0$$

$$\textcircled{i} \Rightarrow \vec{\nabla}_0 \left[\frac{r}{f} \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 + \omega \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t \right] = 0$$

$$\nabla^2 \phi_t = \frac{1}{2} (F^{\phi r} F_{tr} + F^{\phi z} F_{tz})$$

(M/6)

$$[F^{\phi r}] = F_{\alpha\beta} g^{\alpha\phi} g^{\beta r} = F_{\phi\beta} g^{\phi\phi} g^{\beta r} + F_{t\beta} g^{\beta\phi} g^{\beta r} = F_{\phi r} g^{\phi\phi} g^{rr} + F_{tr} g^{\beta\phi} g^{rr} =$$

$$= \ominus \partial_r A_\phi \cdot \frac{f}{r^2} \cdot \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \ominus \partial_r A_t \cdot \frac{f\omega}{r^2} \cdot \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} = \ominus \frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} [\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \partial_r A_t] = \boxed{\ominus \frac{f}{r e^{2\gamma}} \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \partial_r A_t) \right]}$$

$$[F^{\phi z}] = F_{\alpha\beta} g^{\alpha\phi} g^{\beta z} = F_{\phi\beta} g^{\phi\phi} g^{\beta z} + F_{t\beta} g^{\beta\phi} g^{\beta z} = F_{\phi z} g^{\phi\phi} g^{zz} + F_{tz} g^{\beta\phi} g^{zz} =$$

$$= \ominus \partial_z A_\phi \cdot \frac{f}{r^2} \cdot \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \ominus \partial_z A_t \cdot \frac{f\omega}{r^2} \cdot \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} = \boxed{\ominus \frac{f}{r e^{2\gamma}} \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + \omega \partial_z A_t) \right]}$$

$$[F^{\phi r} \cdot F_{tr}] = \frac{f}{r e^{2\gamma}} \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \partial_r A_t) \right] \cdot \partial_r A_t$$

$$[F^{\phi z} \cdot F_{tz}] = \frac{f}{r e^{2\gamma}} \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + \omega \partial_z A_t) \right] \cdot \partial_z A_t$$

$$\ominus \frac{1}{2} \frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \left[\partial_r \cdot \frac{df}{dz} \frac{d\omega}{dz} + r f \cdot \frac{d^2 \omega}{dz^2} \ominus f \cdot \frac{d\omega}{dr} + 2r \frac{df}{dr} \frac{d\omega}{dr} + r f \cdot \frac{d^2 \omega}{dr^2} \right] = \frac{f}{2 r e^{2\gamma}} \left[\frac{f}{r} (\dots) \right] / \cdot \left(\frac{f}{r} \right)$$

$$\ominus \frac{f^2}{r^2} \left[2r \frac{df}{dz} \frac{d\omega}{dz} + r f \frac{d^2 \omega}{dz^2} \ominus f \frac{d\omega}{dr} + 2r \frac{df}{dr} \frac{d\omega}{dr} + r f \frac{d^2 \omega}{dr^2} \right] = \left[\frac{f}{r} \right]$$

$$\ominus \left[\frac{2f}{r} \frac{df}{dz} \frac{d\omega}{dz} + \frac{f^2}{r} \frac{d^2 \omega}{dz^2} \ominus \frac{f^2}{r^2} \frac{d\omega}{dr} + \frac{2f}{r} \frac{df}{dr} \frac{d\omega}{dr} + \frac{f^2}{r} \frac{d^2 \omega}{dr^2} \right] = \frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \partial_r A_t) + \frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + \omega \partial_z A_t)$$

$$\ominus \frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \frac{d\omega}{dz} \right] \ominus \frac{d}{dr} \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \frac{d\omega}{dr} \right] = \frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \partial_r A_t) + \frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + \omega \partial_z A_t)$$

$$\left| \frac{d}{dr} \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \frac{dw}{dr} \right] = \frac{2f}{r} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right) \ominus \frac{f^2}{r^2} \frac{dw}{dr} + \frac{f^2}{r^2} \left(\frac{d^2 w}{dr^2} \right) \right|$$

(M/7)

$$\left| \frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \frac{dw}{dz} \right] = \frac{2f}{r} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right) \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right) + \frac{f^2}{r} \frac{d^2 w}{dz^2} \right|$$

$$\ominus \frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right) \right] \ominus \frac{d}{dr} \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right) \right] = \frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + r \omega \partial_r A_t) \cdot \partial_r A_t + \frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + r \omega \partial_z A_t) \cdot \partial_z A_t$$

$$\partial_r [\sqrt{-g}] F^{rt} + \partial_z [\sqrt{-g}] F^{zt} = 0$$

$$\partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + r \omega \partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + r \omega \partial_z A_t) \right] = 0$$

$$\textcircled{P} = \frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_t) (\partial_r A_\phi + r \omega \partial_r A_t) + \frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_t) (\partial_z A_\phi + r \omega \partial_z A_t) \Rightarrow$$

$$\Rightarrow \partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} A_t (\partial_r A_\phi + r \omega \partial_r A_t) \right] = \partial_r A_t \cdot \frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + r \omega \partial_r A_t) + A_t \cdot \partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + r \omega \partial_r A_t) \right]$$

$$\textcircled{+} \partial_z \left[\frac{f}{r} A_t (\partial_z A_\phi + r \omega \partial_z A_t) \right] = \partial_z A_t \cdot \frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + r \omega \partial_z A_t) + A_t \cdot \partial_z \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + r \omega \partial_z A_t) \right]$$

$$= \partial_r A_t \cdot \frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + r \omega \partial_r A_t) + \partial_z A_t \cdot \frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + r \omega \partial_z A_t) + A_t \left\{ \partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + r \omega \partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + r \omega \partial_z A_t) \right] \right\}$$

|| 0 because $\partial_r [\sqrt{-g}] F^{rt} = 0$!

$$\textcircled{P} = \partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} A_t (\partial_r A_\phi + r \omega \partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\frac{f}{r} A_t (\partial_z A_\phi + r \omega \partial_z A_t) \right]$$

$$\textcircled{\ominus} \frac{d}{dz} \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \left(\frac{d\psi}{dz} \right) \right] \textcircled{\ominus} \frac{d}{dr} \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \left(\frac{d\psi}{dr} \right) \right] = \partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} A_t (\partial_r A_\phi + r\omega \partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\frac{f}{r} A_t (\partial_z A_\phi + r\omega \partial_z A_t) \right]$$

↓

(1/8)

$$\vec{\nabla}_0 \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \vec{\nabla} \psi + \frac{f}{r} A_t (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + r\omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \right] = 0$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \doteq (\partial_r, \partial_z)$$

$$\rightarrow \cancel{R}_t^\phi = \cancel{\Gamma}_t^\phi$$

$$\Phi = A_t \ominus i \tilde{A}_3$$

$$\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 = \frac{f}{r} (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + r \vec{\nabla} A_t)$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_\perp (\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3) = 0 \rightarrow \text{gauge conditions}$$

(1/9)

$$\Phi^* = A_t + i \tilde{A}_3$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \Phi = \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus i \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3$$

$$\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi = (A_t + i \tilde{A}_3) (\vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus i \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3) = A_t \cdot \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus \underline{i A_t \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3} + \underline{i \tilde{A}_3 \cdot \vec{\nabla} A_t}$$

$$\mathcal{L}(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi) = \tilde{A}_3 \cdot \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus A_t \cdot \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3$$

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{e}_\phi \times \mathcal{L}(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi) &= \vec{e}_\phi \times (\tilde{A}_3 \vec{\nabla} A_t) \ominus \vec{e}_\phi \times (A_t \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3) = \\ &= \tilde{A}_3 \cdot \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus A_t \cdot \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{f}{r} (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + r \vec{\nabla} A_t)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} [\vec{e}_\phi \times \mathcal{L}(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)] = \vec{\nabla} [\tilde{A}_3 \cdot \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus A_t \cdot \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3] = \vec{\nabla} A_t (\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3)$$

$$\vec{\nabla}_\perp \left[\frac{f^2}{r} \vec{\nabla} \omega \ominus \vec{e}_\phi \times \mathcal{L}(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi) \right] = 0$$

Def. of h-potential

$$\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} h = \frac{f^2}{r} \vec{\nabla} \omega \ominus \vec{e}_\phi \times \mathcal{L}(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)$$

$$\underbrace{\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} h}_{= \ominus \vec{\nabla} h} = \frac{f^2}{r} \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \omega \ominus \underbrace{\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{e}_\phi \times \mathcal{L}(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)}_{= \mathcal{L}(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)} \Rightarrow \ominus [\vec{\nabla} h + \mathcal{L}(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)] = \frac{f^2}{r} \vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \omega$$

$$\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \omega = \ominus \frac{r}{f^2} [\vec{\nabla} h + \mathcal{L}(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)]$$

$$\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \psi = \ominus \frac{r}{f^2} [\vec{\nabla} h + \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)] \cdot \vec{\nabla}$$

$$\vec{\nabla} [\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \psi] = 0$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \left[\frac{r}{f^2} (\vec{\nabla} h + \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)) \right] = 0$$

where the potential (h) is defined as follows:

$$\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} h = \frac{f^2}{r} \vec{\nabla} \psi \ominus \vec{e}_\phi \times \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)$$

$$\Phi = A_2 \ominus i A_3$$

M/10

$$\mathbb{T}_{ij}(F) = \frac{1}{2} F_{i\alpha} F_j^\alpha \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{ij} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}$$

M/M

$$\mathbb{T}_{tt}(F) = \frac{1}{2} F_{t\alpha} F_t^\alpha \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{tt} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}$$

$$F_{t\alpha} F_t^\alpha = F_{tr} F_t^r + F_{tz} F_t^z = F_{tr} \cdot F_{tr} \cdot g^{rr} + F_{tz} \cdot F_{tz} \cdot g^{zz} = \left[(\partial_r A_t)^2 \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} + (\partial_z A_t)^2 \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \right]$$

$$F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} = F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\beta\alpha} + F_{r\alpha\beta} F^{r\alpha\beta} + F_{\phi\alpha\beta} F^{\phi\alpha\beta} + F_{z\alpha\beta} F^{z\alpha\beta} =$$

$$= \underline{F_{tr} F^{tr}} + \underline{F_{tz} F^{tz}} + \underline{F_{r\phi} F^{r\phi}} + \underline{F_{r\phi} F^{r\phi}} + \underline{F_{\phi z} F^{\phi z}} + \underline{F_{\phi z} F^{\phi z}} + \underline{F_{z\phi} F^{z\phi}} + \underline{F_{zt} F^{zt}}$$

$$= 2(F_{tr} F^{tr} + F_{tz} F^{tz} + F_{r\phi} F^{r\phi} + F_{z\phi} F^{z\phi})$$

$$F^{tr} = F_{\alpha\beta} \cdot g^{t\alpha} \cdot g^{r\beta} = F_{\alpha\beta} \cdot g^{tt} \cdot g^{r\alpha} + F_{\alpha\beta} \cdot g^{t\phi} \cdot g^{r\alpha} =$$

$$= F_{tr} \cdot g^{tt} \cdot g^{rr} + F_{\phi r} \cdot g^{t\phi} \cdot g^{rr} = (\ominus \partial_r A_t) \left(\frac{f \omega^2 \ominus r^2}{r^2} \right) \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} + (\ominus \partial_r A_\phi) \cdot \frac{f \omega}{r^2} \cdot \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} =$$

$$= \ominus \partial_r A_t \left(\frac{f \omega^2 \ominus r^2}{e^{2\gamma} \cdot r^2} \right) \ominus \partial_r A_\phi \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}}$$

$$F_{tr} \cdot F^{tr} = \left(\partial_r A_t \right)^2 \left[\frac{f \omega^2 \ominus r^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \right] + (\partial_r A_t) (\partial_r A_\phi) \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}}$$

$$F^{r\phi} = F_{\alpha\beta} g^{\alpha r} g^{\beta\phi} = F_{r\psi} g^{\psi r} g^{\beta\phi} = F_{r\phi} g^{\psi r} g^{\beta\phi} + F_{r\psi} g^{\psi r} g^{\beta\phi} =$$

(M/12)

$$= (\partial_r A_\phi) \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \frac{f}{r^2} + (\partial_r A_t) \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \frac{f\omega}{r^2} = (\partial_r A_\phi) \frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} + \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} (\partial_r A_t)$$

$$F_{r\phi} F^{r\phi} = (\partial_r A_\phi)^2 \frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} + \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} (\partial_r A_\phi) (\partial_r A_t)$$

$$T_{tt} = \frac{1}{2} F_{\alpha\lambda} F_{\alpha\lambda} - \frac{1}{2} g_{tt} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}$$

$$\frac{1}{2} F_{\alpha\lambda} F_{\alpha\lambda} g^{tt} - \frac{1}{2} g_{tt} (2F_{r\phi} F^{r\phi} + 2F_{r\psi} F^{r\psi}) = \frac{1}{2e^{2\gamma}} f (\partial_r A_t)^2 +$$

$$\oplus \frac{1}{4} f \left[(\partial_r A_t)^2 \left(\frac{f^2 \omega^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} - r^2 \right) + (\partial_r A_t) (\partial_r A_\phi) \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} + (\partial_r A_\phi)^2 \frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} + \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} (\partial_r A_\phi) (\partial_r A_t) \right] =$$

$$= \frac{f}{2e^{2\gamma}} (\partial_r A_t)^2 \oplus \frac{f}{4e^{2\gamma}} (\partial_r A_t)^2 \oplus \frac{1}{4} f \left[(\partial_r A_t)^2 \frac{f^2 \omega^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} + (\partial_r A_t) (\partial_r A_\phi) \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} + (\partial_r A_\phi)^2 \frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \right] =$$

$$= \frac{1}{4} \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} (\partial_r A_t)^2 \oplus \frac{1}{4} f \cdot \frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \left[(\partial_r A_t)^2 \omega^2 + 2 (\partial_r A_t) \omega \cdot (\partial_r A_\phi) + (\partial_r A_\phi)^2 \right]$$

$$= \left[(\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right]^2$$

$$= \frac{1}{4} \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} (\partial_r A_t)^2 \oplus \frac{1}{4} \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \left(\frac{f^2}{r^2} \right) \left[(\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right]^2$$

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \left\{ \rho_4 \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] \ominus r^2 \left[\left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + r^2 f \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right] \right\} =$$

(1/12)

$$= \frac{1}{4} \frac{f}{e^{\gamma}} \left[(\partial_r A_t)^2 + (\partial_z A_t)^2 \right] + \frac{1}{4} \frac{f}{e^{\gamma}} \left(\frac{f^2}{r^2} \right) \left\{ \left[(\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right]^2 + \left[(\partial_z A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_z A_t) \right]^2 \right\}$$

$$\uparrow = (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \circ (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \uparrow$$

$$\frac{\rho_4}{r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] \ominus \left[\left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + f \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right] =$$

$$= \frac{f}{4} \left[(\partial_r A_t)^2 + (\partial_z A_t)^2 \right] + \frac{1}{4} \frac{f^3}{r^2} \left[(\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \circ (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \right]$$

$$\downarrow \uparrow \vec{\nabla} = (\partial_r, \partial_z) \uparrow$$

$$\frac{\rho_4}{r^2} (\vec{\nabla} w)^2 \ominus (\vec{\nabla} f)^2 + f \nabla^2 f = \frac{f}{4} (\vec{\nabla} A_t)^2 + \frac{f^3}{4r^2} \left[(\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \circ (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \right]$$

$$\frac{f^4}{r^2} (\vec{\nabla} \omega)^2 \ominus (\vec{\nabla} f)^2 + f \nabla^2 f = \frac{f}{4} (\vec{\nabla} A_t)^2 + \frac{f}{4} \left[\left(\frac{f}{r} \right) (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \cdot \left(\frac{f}{r} \right) (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t) \right] \uparrow$$

(M/14)

$$\boxed{\Phi = A_t \ominus i \tilde{A}_3}$$

$$\boxed{\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3 = \frac{f}{r} (\vec{\nabla} A_\phi + \omega \vec{\nabla} A_t)}$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \Phi \cdot \vec{\nabla} \Phi^* = (\vec{\nabla} A_t \ominus i \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3) (\vec{\nabla} A_t + i \vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3) = (\vec{\nabla} A_t)^2 + (\vec{\nabla} \tilde{A}_3)^2$$

$$\boxed{\frac{f}{4} \vec{\nabla} \Phi \cdot \vec{\nabla} \Phi^*} \Rightarrow \textcircled{\Phi}$$

$$\boxed{\vec{e}_\phi \times \vec{\nabla} \omega = \ominus \frac{r}{f^2} [\vec{\nabla} h + \int_{\text{Im}} (\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)]}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (\varepsilon^{i\phi_1 m} \partial_{\phi_1} \nabla_m \omega) \varepsilon_{i\phi_2 k} \partial_{\phi_2} \nabla^k \omega = \\ & = \varepsilon^{i\phi_1 m} \varepsilon_{i\phi_2 k} \underbrace{\partial_{\phi_1} \partial_{\phi_2} \nabla_m \omega \nabla^k \omega}_{\text{circled}} = \left(\partial_{\phi_2}^j \partial_{\phi_1}^m \ominus \partial_{\phi_2}^m \partial_{\phi_1}^j \right) \textcircled{\partial_{\phi_1} \partial_{\phi_2} \nabla_m \omega \nabla^k \omega} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_{i\alpha k} \cdot e^a \nabla_\omega^k \cdot \varepsilon^{i\beta l} e_\beta \cdot \nabla_\omega l &= (\partial_a^b \partial_\omega^l \ominus \partial_a^l \partial_\omega^b) \nabla_\omega^k \nabla_\omega l \underbrace{e_a^k e_\beta^l}_{\text{circled}} = \\ &= \nabla_\omega^k \nabla_\omega l \underbrace{(e^a e_\beta \cdot \partial_a^b)}_1 \ominus \nabla_\omega^k \nabla_\omega l \cdot \underbrace{\partial_a^b}_{\partial \phi} \cdot \underbrace{e^a e_\beta}_{\partial \phi} = \underline{\underline{(\nabla_\omega^k \nabla_\omega l)}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{\left(\frac{r^2}{f^2} \right) [\vec{\nabla} h + \int_{\text{Im}} (\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)] = (\vec{\nabla} \omega)^2}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{f^4}{r^2} (\vec{\nabla} \omega)^2 = \frac{f^4}{r^2} \cdot \frac{r^2}{f^2} [\vec{\nabla} h + \int_{\text{Im}} (\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)]^2$$

$$\boxed{[\vec{\nabla} h + \int_{\text{Im}} (\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)]^2 \ominus (\vec{\nabla} f)^2 + f \nabla^2 f = \frac{f}{4} \vec{\nabla} \Phi \cdot \vec{\nabla} \Phi^*}$$

$$\Phi = a + ib$$

$$\Phi^* = a - ib$$

M/15

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi} &= (a - ib) \vec{\nabla} (a + ib) = (a - ib) [\vec{\nabla}_a + i \vec{\nabla}_b] = a \vec{\nabla}_a + i a \vec{\nabla}_b + i b \vec{\nabla}_a + b \vec{\nabla}_b = \\ &= a \vec{\nabla}_a + b \vec{\nabla}_b + i [b \vec{\nabla}_a + a \vec{\nabla}_b] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{\Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^*} &= (a + ib) \vec{\nabla} (a - ib) = (a + ib) [\vec{\nabla}_a - i \vec{\nabla}_b] = a \vec{\nabla}_a - i a \vec{\nabla}_b - i b \vec{\nabla}_a + b \vec{\nabla}_b = \\ &= a \vec{\nabla}_a + b \vec{\nabla}_b - i [a \vec{\nabla}_b + b \vec{\nabla}_a] \end{aligned}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi) &= b \vec{\nabla}_a + a \vec{\nabla}_b \\ \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^*) &= a \vec{\nabla}_b - b \vec{\nabla}_a \end{aligned} \right\} \Rightarrow \boxed{\mathcal{I}_m(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi) = \ominus \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^*)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi + \Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^*} &= \underbrace{2(a \vec{\nabla}_a + b \vec{\nabla}_b)}_{\parallel} \ominus \underbrace{2(a \vec{\nabla}_a + b \vec{\nabla}_b)}_{\parallel} \ominus 2i [b \vec{\nabla}_a + a \vec{\nabla}_b] = \\ \ominus 2 \Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi &= 2i [a \vec{\nabla}_b - b \vec{\nabla}_a] = 2i \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^*) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi + \Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^* \ominus 2 \Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi &= \\ = 2i \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^*) \end{aligned}$$

$$\ominus 2 \Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^* = \ominus 2 [a \vec{\nabla}_a + b \vec{\nabla}_b + i (a \vec{\nabla}_b - b \vec{\nabla}_a)]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \boxed{\Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^* + \Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi \ominus 2 \Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^*} &= \cancel{2(a \vec{\nabla}_a + b \vec{\nabla}_b)} \ominus \cancel{2(a \vec{\nabla}_a + b \vec{\nabla}_b)} \ominus 2i (a \vec{\nabla}_b - b \vec{\nabla}_a) = \\ &= \ominus 2i (a \vec{\nabla}_b - b \vec{\nabla}_a) = 2i (b \vec{\nabla}_a - a \vec{\nabla}_b) = 2i \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi) \end{aligned}$$

$$\boxed{\Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^* + \Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi \ominus 2 \Phi \vec{\nabla} \Phi^* = 2i \mathcal{I}_m(\Phi^* \vec{\nabla} \Phi)}$$